

RENEWABLE ENERGIES AND THEIR CHALLENGES: UNCERTAINTY AND VARIABILITY OF THE WIND AND SOLAR RESOURCE

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Variability and uncertainty in the wind and solar generation.

Variability and uncertainty are two key factors to take in mind for the generation of energy from renewable sources. The first one involves all inconsistent behavior of a phenomenon due to the change in a condition. Uncertainty, on the other hand, refers to the difficulty of accurately predicting the behavior patterns of an object of study.

There is a limit in the maximum generation for renewable energy plants, which changes over time (variability) and cannot be predicted with perfect precision (uncertainty). Environmentally important net benefits associated with this type of generation can be identified, however, given the great uncertainty and variability of its resources, its integration into electrical systems is currently a great challenge.

The intermittence could cause that the demand of the electrical system remains unsatisfied, which depends on the capacity of storage and the form of operation of each system. This leads to the need to maintain a balance between electricity generation and demand. To prevent it from becoming a problem, it is necessary to anticipate this phenomenon.

Unlike conventional technologies (such as coal, gas and diesel), generation through renewable resources is characterized by being variable and dependent on climatic conditions, with solar energy being the most stable and least risky in economic terms and resource to exploit, while wind energy is the one that presents more challenges, because its forecasts will be less successful as the time lapse between the estimate and the present increases. However, today, countries such as Spain, Holland, Germany and United States, have designed prediction models that integrate the historical references of measurement antennas, along with mathematical iterations

based on data collected in real time, therefore, the margins of error in their forecasts are lower than the world average.

As the generation based on renewable energies reaches higher levels of penetration in the global energy matrix, sufficient forecasts must be taken to avoid an increase in the effects of the variability on the power systems and their respective managements.

Potential impacts of the income of renewable energy in the power system.

The increase in the exploitation of renewable energy sources leads to the need to increase the availability of plants that can produce energy permanently, in order to have the capacity to respond to energy at times when renewable power plants are not available. A greater wind and solar participation imply that the power plants have to operate at lower levels of production or have electricity storage systems to allow the entry of renewable energy. Therefore, it is essential to study the different support alternatives that allow reducing the economic impacts of a greater penetration of renewable energies [1].

The increase in renewable energies also leads to the need to increase the capacity of the transmission system, in order to manage greater electricity flows in the event of a lack of energy caused by the uncertain availability of intermittent generators [2].

With regard to distribution, in order to manage the interaction between variability in flows and in demand, important investments in information technologies necessary to optimize the daily operation of the electric system are required [3]. This could be solved in part with investments in smart meter infrastructure. Usually, the synchronization of the systems is done through global positioning systems (GPS) in order to obtain accurate data for network management [4].

Increase in the probability of failure.

Traditionally, every electric power system has some margin of maneuver to respond to contingencies, depending on its form of operation and storage capacity. However, as the energy matrix becomes more diversified and renewable energies are given more importance, the probability of failure of the systems also increases due to a greater number of intrinsically variable and intermittent power plants, which tend to hinder the necessary balance between electricity produced and consumed. Minimal alterations of this perfect equilibrium can, among other things, generate sudden variations in frequency that would affect the stability of the power systems.

In case of not being adequately invested in reserve generation, which allows immediate availability of energy in the event of any contingency, and in transmission and distribution systems capable of withstanding problems related to intermittency, failures in the system may occur.

Alternative of support and storage.

Broadly speaking, the generation based on diesel and natural gas can be used to

support the variability of renewable energies, because these technologies allow a fast response to contingencies, so they are especially useful to compensate for unpredictable oscillations, especially of the wind generation.

Diesel plants tend to provide a fast response regardless of the condition, but the cost of their operation is relatively high, on the other hand, natural gas plants require a minimum or medium capacity to offer a rapid response to a contingency.

	Coal	Natural Gas in Combined Cycle (NGCC)	Diesel	Hydraulic power
Assumptions for the calculation of costs				
Central investment (USD/kW)	2300	800	500	3000
Cost of operation (USD/MWh)	40	70	250	5
Useful life (years)	40	20	20	40
Capacity factor (original)	90%	90%	90%	70%
Capacity factor (backup)	78%	74%	70%	70%
Leveled cost				
LCOE original (USD/MWh)	70	82	257	55
LCOE backup (USD/MWh)	74	84	260	55

Cost of energy backup technologies. Pontificia Universidad Católica Chile (PUCCh).

Energy storage technologies.

Conceptually, the storage systems are responsible for capturing the energy of the network when there is a generation surplus and then dispatching it when there are a deficit and high costs. In general, the marginal costs of electric power in a power system is calculated every hour, and the idea is to account for the energy requirements at all times.

Nowadays, the pumping of water from reservoirs or PHS (Pumped Hydro Storage) and the storage of energy through compressed air or CAES (Compressed Air Energy Storage) are the only systems developed for commercial exploitation on a large scale.

Another storage system that has recently increased its popularity is the flywheels of inertia, which store kinetic energy through the rotation of a mass with very little loss of energy by friction. A motor generator accelerates the mass to obtain the kinetic energy. Among the advantages of this technology are its rapid response, efficiency close to 70%, few space limitations for its installation and low maintenance cost, on the other hand, its initial acquisition costs per kWh are high, coupled with the fact that its Useful life is short and are not attractive for a large-scale power grid. Its most widespread use is to support small-scale wind generation due to its rapid activation before abrupt fluctuations.

There is another way to store energy and it is through batteries, these provide a quick response for changes in demand to which the power system may be subject, they have no limitation to be located and they have a high energy storage ratio in comparison with the physical space. Currently, among the most popular alternatives as

a complement to the generation based on renewable resources are those composed of sodium sulfide (NAS), lead-acid (Pb - Acid), lithium-ion (Li-ion), vanadium redox (VRB), zinc-bromine (Zn-Br), zinc-air (Zn-Air), sodium-nickel-chlorine (NaNiCl₂) and ferro-chromium (Fe-Cr), however, are the NAS type most popular, being its most widespread use serving as support for distribution networks and as a complement to wind farms. By 2017, approximately 320 MW of installations with NAS batteries were installed worldwide, representing a few more than 1,900 MWh of generation

Technology	LCOE (\$/MWh)
PHS	160 – 220
CAES	120 – 210
flywheels	385
NAS	259 – 294
Lead-acid	320 – 1680
Li-ion	680 – 1150
VRB	420 – 805
Zn-Br	195 – 880
Zn-Air	160 – 200
NaNiCl ₂	310 – 905
Fe-Cr	65 - 248

Cost of energy storage technologies.

Results.

To compare technologies today, it is necessary to translate the impact that these would have on the level costs of renewable energies. To illustrate this, we will analyze what happens when planning supported generation systems, distinguishing what happens with wind power plants compared to solar power plants. To make this comparison you must know the investment required by the renewable energy plants, the original plant factor (% of the hours of a year that the plant works without backup) and the plant factor with backup (% of the hours of a year that the plant can operate thanks to the backup)

Assumptions	Wind farm	Solar plant
Capacity factor (original)	30%	30%
Capacity factor (with backup)	minimum 65%	minimum 65%
Investment	2200 USD/kW	1800 USD/kW

Characteristics of renewable energy

Backup technologies	Backup efficiency	MW to be installed (RREE)	Backup MW	Storage MW	System RREE %	Capacity factor (System)
Coal	100%	38	63	Not applicable	19%	71%
NG CC	100%	38	48	Not applicable	24%	68%
Diésel	100%	38	38	Not applicable	30%	65%
PHS	77%	49	Not applicable	10,9	100%	65%
CAES	50%	76	Not applicable	16,8	100%	65%
Flywheels	92%	41	Not applicable	9,1	100%	65%
NAS	88%	43	Not applicable	9,5	100%	65%

Parameters of backup and accumulation systems

Economically speaking, the only technology that can maintain - even lower - the level of costs for pure wind generation is natural gas in combined cycle, the rest of the options would imply at least double the cost of energy. For a photovoltaic solar generation there are three alternatives that allow to maintain or reduce costs in relation to 100% solar systems, this thanks to the fact that their oscillations are more predictable, being able to rely on Natural Gas, reservoir or coal.

It can be determined that the most expected impact on system costs (due to the intensive exploitation of renewable energies) corresponds to the fact that the support is mainly with diesel. This implies an increase in the level cost more than doubled.

Conclusions.

During the course of the next 5 - 10 years, society will witness how the use of renewable sources will take on an even greater importance than it currently has, especially wind and solar (thermal and photovoltaic), given that their leveled cost have been reduced considerably and there is a high availability of these resources.

A high participation of RREE within the electrical matrix can increase the risk of system failure if its energy redundancy is not increased. In addition, with the current incentives, it is likely that the technologies used to support renewable energy plants will be based on diesel, which will imply an increase in marginal costs and an increase in the number of contracts signed in national electrical systems

It is possible a backup at minimum cost for the renewable energies, for example, for the solar photovoltaic case the hydroelectricity of the reservoir, coal-fired power plants, and combined-cycle natural gas power plants would be used, and in the case of wind power plants, the only alternative to reasonable costs would be the central based in natural gas.

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